

Deliverable 6.6
Software Contribution to Open-Source Projects

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Revision History

Revision	Date	Editor / Commentator	Description of Edits
0.1	2024-10-04	Joss Armstrong (LMI)	Draft ToC of the deliverable
0.2	2025-04-09	Partners contributions on their sections	First draft
0.3	2025-05-26	Joss Armstrong (LMI)	Finalised contributions
0..4	2025-05-27	Joss Armstrong (LMI)	Removed contributions recorded in D4.4
0.5	2025-06-30	Joss Armstrong (LMI)	Ready for final review
0.9	2025-09-11	Jesus Gutierrez (IHP), Mir Ghoraihi (GIGASYS)	Final review and proof-reading
1.0	2025-09-11	Simon Pryor (ACC)	Submission to EUC portal

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List of Acronyms

5GPPP	5G Public Private Partnership
6G-IA	6G Industry Association
AI	Artificial Intelligence
B5G	Beyond 5G
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communications
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
ORAN	Open Radio Access Network
OSC	O-RAN Software Community
PoC	Proof-of-Concept
RAN	Radio Access Network
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
UPF	User Plane Function

Executive Summary

This deliverable, BeGREEN D6.6, “Software contributions in the open-source projects”, includes details on the software contributions performed to open-source projects associated to the developed technologies.

1 Contributions to Open Source Projects

BeGREEN contributions to Open-Source projects and activities are listed in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1 BeGREEN Contributions to Open-Source

Open-Source	Contributing Partner	Contribution Description	Contribution Type
OAI	I2CAT	OpenAirInterface (OAI) Spring of Code. Contribution to the development of E2 SM. Third prize	Code

I2CAT participated in the Spring of Code¹ event hosted by OpenAirInterface (OAI) Software Alliance (OSA) and SLICES-RI. The objective was to contribute to enhancing network management capabilities on the FlexRIC near-RT RIC platform by improving the RAN Control Service Model (SM) to manage functionalities via E2 control procedures through xApps. The contributions follow:

- Developed an xApp to request UE Radio Resource Control (RRC) messages, specifically the RRC Initial Request. Once a UE's initial request is detected, the message information, including the RRC message, IMSI, and TMSI, is forwarded to the xApp.
- Modified the E2 agent code to retrieve the RRC message and updated the code on the gNodeB component of OAI to parse the RRC message for the agent. This was aligned with the O-RAN specifications of the RAN Control E2 service model [1].
- Added REPORT Service Style 1 to the agent, which provides a copy of the complete message according to section 7.4.5 of the specification. This was integrated into FlexRIC alongside the existing REPORT Service Style 1 ("UE Information" - section 7.4.5) and CONTROL Service Style 1 ("Radio Bearer Control" - section 7.6.2) defined in [1].
- The OAI and FlexRIC code contributions have also been integrated to the main code: https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/oai/openairinterface5g/-/merge_requests/3153/commits (OAI) https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/mosaic5g/flexric/-/merge_requests/59/commits (FlexRIC)

I2CAT's contribution was one of the winning solutions in the event².

¹ <https://slices-sc.eu/events/oai-2024-spring-of-code/>

² <https://openairinterface.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/OAI-2024-Summer-Newsletter-1.pdf>

2 Software releases

BeGREEN software releases are summarized in Table 2-1.

Table 2-1: BeGREEN software releases

Type of Contribution	Contributing Partner	Associated Publication	DOI
Source code release	NEC	Ayala-Romero, J. A., Garcia-Saavedra, A., & Costa-Perez, X. (2024, March). Risk-aware continuous control with neural contextual bandits. In <i>Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence</i> (Vol. 38, No. 19, pp. 20930-20938).	10.5281/zenodo.10686581
Source code release	NEC	Ayala-Romero, J. A., Schiavo, L. L., Garcia-Saavedra, A., & Costa-Perez, X. (2024, May). Mean-field multi-agent contextual bandit for energy-efficient resource allocation in vrans. In <i>IEEE INFOCOM 2024-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications</i> (pp. 911-920). IEEE.	10.5281/zenodo.10686512

The first repository provides the complete implementation of the model called Risk-Aware Neural Contextual Bandit (RANCB), as presented in the paper, "*Risk-Aware Continuous Control with Neural Contextual Bandits*" presented at the 38th Annual AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence 2024. It includes the full training and evaluation pipeline, enabling a direct replication of the reported benchmarks. The second contribution is the source code for the Energy-aware learning strategy for Computing Offloading in vRANs (ECORAN) model from our work, "*Mean-Field Multi-Agent Contextual Bandit for Energy-Efficient Resource Allocation in vRANs*", presented at the IEEE International Conference on Computer Communications (INFOCOM) 2024. This repository similarly contains the model implementation, data preprocessing scripts, training configurations, and evaluation code, facilitating a comprehensive reproduction of our findings. Both repositories are well-documented to guide users through the setup and execution process.

To facilitate proper attribution and ensure long-term accessibility, each software repository has been archived and assigned a persistent Digital Object Identifier (DOI) via Zenodo. These software contributions are intended to provide researchers with the necessary tools to fully replicate our experimental results, validate our proposed methodologies, and serve as a foundation for future research.

3 Summary and Conclusions

This document, BeGREEN D6.6, includes the contributions from the Consortium to open-source projects.

There has also been consideration within BeGREEN of adding the AI Engine and non-real-time RIC developed in the project to the O-RAN Software Community (OSC)

4 Bibliography

[1] O-RAN Alliance, E2 Service Model (E2SM) for RAN Control; Technical Specification ORAN-WG3.E2SM-RC-R004-v07.00, O-RAN Working Group 3, O-RAN Alliance, 2024.